

SUSTAINABLE SMART PORT DEVELOPMENT: HOW TO CREATE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE TO THAI PORTS AND DEVELOPING TO BE GREEN AND SMART PORT

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Abstract

Global ports and maritime shipping industry are important carriers for global supply chain networks. While modern seaports have a significant role in supply chain for the competitiveness of each country in terms of smart and green. Ports have been specially challenged during the COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 pandemic. The research reveals that green and smart port is major driven to survive in intense competition in global dynamic changes. The key to improving the sustainability of the shipping industry lies in green and smart port initiatives. Ports worldwide are feeling the need to become environmentally friendly, whether by transitioning to Net Zero Carbon, reducing emissions, or operating more efficiently and sustainably. This paper explores current status of Thai ports, and future direction of seaport and maritime transport in next decade. It studies role of seaports, especially Thai port to drive economic growth and to create national competitiveness. It also examines what factors influencing to future port development. It studies how port can adapt and survive sustainably in global changes and disruptions. To achieve the objectives, the study collects data in three dimensions, literature review is primarily conducted in issues related with ports' role in maritime transport and shipping industry, how to become smart port in global changes. What is future direction of smart port development. Secondly, survey method is used to examine issues and relationships between studying variables. Finally, in-depth interview is conducted to obtain more deep information from port user, port provider and port regulator. The population consisted of 90 companies in Thailand. Deploying random stratified sampling, questionnaires are distributed to 110 companies. After a month, there are 90 questionnaires returned with 81.8 per cent response rate. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and port effectiveness and efficiency, and sustainable growth (Y). Developing port to be green and smart port, it increasingly provides port effectiveness and efficiency, and increasing sustainable growth. It also reveals that there is a relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and technological changes and disruptions (Z). It is based on hypothesis that green and smart port strategy and management would be adapted consistent with technological changes and disruptions. Further research is recommended to close the future gap.

Keywords: Smart, Green, Port, GHG Emission, Maritime, Transport, Shipping.

1. INTRODUCTION

Global ports and maritime shipping industry are important carriers for global supply chain networks. While modern seaports have a significant role in supply chain for the competitiveness of each country in terms of globalization and connectivity. Ports have been specially challenged during the COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 pandemic.

The research reveals that green and smart port is major driven to survive in intense competition in global dynamic changes. In term of smart port, modern technologies provide the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics processes, hence they create an effective advance which strengthens the port's position among the maritime communities.

Furthermore, the efficiency and safety of the cargo flows highly depend on the related information flows.

In term of green port, the shipping industry is a major contributor to global emissions, but it is also one of the most promising sectors to reduce its environmental footprint. The key to improving the sustainability of the shipping industry lies in green port initiatives. Ports worldwide are feeling the heed to become environmentally friendly, whether by transitioning to Net Zero Carbon, reducing emissions, or operating more efficiently and sustainably.

The initiatives provide a range of measures and strategies to reduce emissions and make operations with automate material handling more efficient, with the end goal of creating a more sustainable port and shipping industry. In this paper examines what green and smart port initiatives are and how they contribute to a sustainable port and shipping industry.

The objective of this paper is to explores current status of Thai ports, and future direction of seaport and maritime transport in next decade. It studies role of seaports, especially Thai port to drive economic growth and to create national competitiveness.

Furthermore, it also examines what factors influencing to future port development and port survival. It studies how port can adapt and survive sustainably in global changes and disruptions. A conceptual model of green and smart ports is designed to facilitate Thai ports for future development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The paper reviews port's role and maritime transport and shipping industry. It examines factors influencing to smart and green port development. Future direction of smart and green port in next decade is evaluated and analyzed. The literature facilitates to provide ground theories to understand status of ports, and future direction of seaport and maritime transport in next decade.

Including factors influencing to future port development and develop a conceptual model develop to enhance port competitiveness. And how ports can adapt and survive sustainably in global changes and disruptions

Port's role and maritime transport and shipping business

Global ports and maritime shipping networks are important driver for global supply chain networks. Modern seaports have a significant role the competitiveness of each country in terms of globalization and connectivity.

During the COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 pandemic have been specially challenged to global ports and maritime shipping. Ports have grown to play a very important role in supply chains.

After 1990, the proposal of a theoretical model, carried out during the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), helped to understand the evolution and role of seaports in maritime transport context. The model considers locally adopted strategies, service provided and information technology to distinguish five generations of ports (Table 1)

Table 1: Evolution of Seaport based on operations of manual to automation

Generation	Duration	Evolution Process	Remark
1 st Generation	Until 1960	Mechanic Port (mechanical operation and handicraft works)	
2 nd Generation	1960	Container port (Industrial and commercial area)	
3 rd Generation	1980	EDI port (traditional service, logistics and total distribution services)	
4 th Generation	2000	Internet port (global network, logistics area, port community, intermodal and internet services)	
5 th Generation	2011	Smart port (sustainable port, smart city and hinterland, multimodal services and logistics community)	

Source: UNCTAD (1994); Kaliszewski, A. (2018); Flynn, M., Lee, P., Notteboom, T. (2011)

Globalization and technological developments have not only affected the design and operations of port facilities, but also the organizational and institutional relationship between members of the port community (Haezendonek, E. Dooms, M., Verbeke, A. 2014; Gonzalez-Laxe. F., Martin-Bernudez., F., Martin-Palmero, F., Nonvo-Corti. (2019). In present, ports face competition between ports and also competition between port terminals. The forces pressure ports to enhance port performance and competitiveness. Further, the increase in social and economic demands is causing that port around the world to incorporate initiatives to reduce environmental impact and improve port operations. Modern technologies provide the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics processes; hence they create an effective advance which strengthens the port’s position among the maritime communities.

Table 2: Evolution of seaport based on pattern of port service provided

Generation	Duration	Evolution Process	Remark
1 st Generation	Before 1980	Port to Port	
2 nd Generation	1980-2000	Door to Door	
3 rd Generation	2000-2020	Full range of logistics services	
4 th Generation	2020-	Full range of logistics services and real estate development	

Source: Taweesak Theppitak, 2023

Table 2 shows evolution of seaport based on pattern of port service provided (Taweesak Theppitak, 2023). Before 1980, ports provided their services to serve vessels for cargo loading and unloading. As ports were mainly designed infrastructure and facilities for berthing and unberthing, no warehouse, container freight station and other facilities. Until 1980, when world trade and shipping industry were rapidly expanding to support economic growth. Containers were popularly used to carry cargoes from exporters to importers. The containers facilitated to transport by door to door. Global ports transformed their infrastructure and facilities to adapt and respond to the changes. However, after 2000, ports provided full maritime logistics operations and management. Many logistics activities were operated within ports and hinterland. Finally, after 2020, most of global ports attempt to optimize their resources, and starting to develop their land uses efficiently. They have also provided full range of logistics services and real estate development.

Factors influencing to smart and green port development

Global ports and maritime shipping networks are important carriers for global supply chain networks, but they are also the main sources of energy consumption and pollution. To limit ship emissions in

ports and offshore areas, the International Maritime Organization, as well as some countries, has issued a series of policies. It highlights the importance and necessity of investigation emergent research problems in the operation management of green ports and maritime shipping networks. Authors points out that factors influencing to adapt and transform to port operation and management are enhancing port efficiency and productivity, technological changes and disruption, build supply chain among players in port community, including managing organizational and institutional relationship between members of the port community. While ports face from pressures by global and national economic situations, geopolitics, Russia-Ukraine Crisis, and world trade wars. Other factor is government, International Maritime Organization, and related associations have also role to enforce ports to provide measure for port safety, security and environment. Finally, increase in social and economic demands is causing that port around the world to incorporate initiatives to reduce environmental impact and improve port operations. In the current study, the review focuses on three areas: operation management and optimization of green and smart ports, optimizing the operation management in green shipping networks, and emission control measures and related policies in green shipping. The relation among these works is also reflected by three categories: port, shipping, and policy on port and shipping.

Future direction of smart port in next decade

Green and smart port is major driven to survive in intense competition in global dynamic changes. A smart port is based on the implementation of behavior strategies that can be classified into four main activity domains: operations, environment, energy, and safety and security (Molavi. A., Lkaras G. J. Race. B., 2020).

Table 3: Smart Port key performance indicators

Description		Key Performance Indicators	
Smart Port Operation	Operational	Operational Efficiency	Total Cargo Moved in Relation to seaport equipment
	Economics	Economic Efficiency	Investments and returns
	Political & Institutional	Management Transparency Private operations (%) Quality private Services SMS	Open data system Concession area index number of private operators with discounts for the quality of their services ISO 9001
	Social	Health and Safety. SMS Labor inclusion and equality in the workforce	ISO 45001 Number of female workers of total workers Gender diversity in the Board of Administration
	Mobility	Optimize the mobility of heavy vehicles Boost rail traffic	Existence of railway tracks inside the port
Environment	Water quality Water consumption management Noise Pollution		EDP ISO14001 EMASIII
Energy	Renewable energy production Energy management system		Use of renewable (wind energy, Solar power) ISO50001
Safety and security	Actions to improve cybersecurity		ISPS

Source: S. Battino and M. del Mar Munoz Leonisio., 2019; Mazzaino, M., Battino, S., Lo sviuppo di trasporto., 2019

As smart port is a broad concept that encompasses different organizations and require a long-term commitment (Theppitak, T., 2023). Three relevant topics have been observed. First, the ability of seaports to evolve under the sustainability and smart paradigm principles was presented. Second, the port city relationship is analyzed through the evolution of technology and global networks and the ports contribution to the creation of incomes in their hinterland. Third, possible mechanisms are studied to reduce the undesirable output of port activity. Implementing smart strategies improves both the operational efficiency and port city relationships.

Furthermore, to become a smart port, ports need to provide modern technologies. The technology provides the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics processes; hence they create an effective advance which strengthens the port's position among the maritime communities. Furthermore, the efficiency and safety of the cargo flows highly depend on the related information flows (Dziula, P., Kolowrocki, K., Soszynska-Budny, J. 2013). The innovative solutions, characterized in the chapter, have been grouped into two main parts: internet of things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Big Data. While IoT concerns devices that interact with the internet, AI makes devices learn from their data. The IoT, as defined by IEEE, is a network of items, including sensors and embedded systems which are connected to the internet and enable physical objects to collect and exchange data (Gubbi, J., Buyya, R., Marusic, S., Palaniswami, M. 2013). It is used in order to optimize the cargo tracking and the process of its delivery, including to optimize container service using RFID. Both systems are considered to change the current port into the smart port in the most quickly way. When creating the article, the following databases were mainly used Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, Research Gate, IEEE Explore, Science Direct. Smart solutions based on artificial intelligence and big data are essential elements of data-driven decision-making process in most industries (Liang, T., P. Liu, Y, H., 2018).

They also can divide into clusters: digitization, which focuses on the use of digital technology in shipping, especially port communication system (PCS). And applications of big data from AIS which focuses on proper visualization of maritime traffic, maritime safety. And energy efficiency (Munim, Z.H., Dushenko, M., Jimenez, V.J., Shakil, M.H., Imset, M. 2020). Concentrates on improving energy efficiency in maritime transport using AI and big data, by optimizing ship speed, route planning, or shipping networks (Brouer, B.D., Karsten, C.V. 2017).

Key technology of AI and big data in port operation and management: port communication system (Long, A. (2009), applications of big data from AIS (Pallotta, G., Vespe, M., Bryan, K. 2013), Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) (Anwar, M., M. Casalichio, E., Henesey, L. (2019), Artificial neural network (Shetty, R., Caceres, R., Pastrana, J., Rabelo, L. 2012), Automated Guide Vehicle (AGV) (Gotting, H.H. 2000), Autonomous Robots (Yuan, S., Skinner, B.T., Huang, S., Liu, D.K., Dissanayake, G., Lau., H., Pagac, D., Pratley, T. 2010), Algorithms (Kozan E, Preston P (2006), and Smart Grid (Iris, C., Lam, J.S.L. 2019).

The literatures led to conclusion that the next generation ports will use automation, electrification and smart energy management system (Iris, C., Lam, J.S.L. 2019). The IoT technology provided smart solutions to storage and monitoring of data at the port. Modern remote sensing technologies such as RFID for identification and location, cameras and built-in computer vision algorithms, can contribute to safer and shorter handling time compared with classic container terminals. Information technologies in logistics allow us to optimize the flow of goods and if a port wants to stay ahead of the competition, it must invest in information technology (Modzelewska, M., Borowski, R. Kaizer, A. 2017).

Over 90% of the world's trade is carried by the shipping network as reported by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2023). The shipping industry is a major contributor to global emissions, but it is also one of the most promising sectors to reduce its environmental

footprint. The key to improving the sustainability of the shipping industry lies in green port initiatives. Green port initiatives provide a range of measures and measures to reduce emissions and make operations more efficient, with the end goal of creating a more sustainable shipping industry. In this article, we'll take a look at what green port initiatives are and how they contribute to a sustainable shipping industry. Ports worldwide are feeling the heat to become environmentally friendly, whether by transitioning to Net Zero Carbon, reducing emissions, or operating more sustainably. The pressure has only intensified during the Covid-19 pandemic, bringing various issues to light and highlighting the importance of building resilience into terminal operations.

However, the frequent shipping activities produce numerous emissions of pollutant and greenhouse gases and is thus a main source of pollution and energy consumption (Theppitak, T., 2023). An important issue at present is achieving the goal of energy saving and emission reduction in ports while improving the service level of these ports. The IMO reported that CO₂ emissions from ships account for nearly 2.6% of the world's annual emissions, whereas SO_x and NO_x emissions from ships account for 13% and 15% of the annual emissions from human activities, respectively (IMO, 2022). IMO continues to contribute to the global fight against climate change, in support of the UN Sustainable Development Goal 13, to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. IMO has adopted mandatory measures to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases from international shipping, under IMO's pollution prevention treaty (MARPOL) - the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) mandatory for new ships, and the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP) (IMO, 2022).

The literature (Molavi, A., Lkaras G. J. Race. B., 2020; Kavakeb S, Nguyen T.T, McGinley K, Yang Z, Jenkinson I, Murray R. 2015; Hall W J. 2010) reveals ports in countries attempting to reduce CO₂ emission. These initiatives include everything from the use of green technology and renewable energy sources to the adoption of sustainable practices and waste management. In the Netherlands, the Port of Rotterdam is an example of a port that has implemented green port initiatives such as using energy-saving light, an energy management system, and modern waste treatment (Mark Buzinkay, 2023). The port has also invested in new technology, such as RFID reader systems for container tracking and electrically operated cranes. These initiatives have helped the port reduce its carbon dioxide emission by 14 per cent since 2016. The Port of Southampton in the UK has implemented eco-friendly initiatives such as air emissions monitoring and reducing the use of Sulphur-based fuel (Theppitak, T., 2023). The port has also worked to develop renewable energy capabilities, such as investing in a new wind farm and a battery storage system. The port has also partnered with the UK government to develop a green port program, which focuses on reducing GHG emissions and improving energy efficiency (Mark Buzinkay, 2023).

Germany's Port of Hamburg has also implemented a number of green port initiatives, such as using renewable energy sources, investing in electric trucks, and using green construction materials (Molavi, A., Lkaras G. J. Race. B., 2020). The port has also implemented a number of waste management strategies, such as using waste heat recovery systems, waste recycling systems, and composting initiatives. Singapore has also invested in green port initiatives. The Port of Singapore has developed a comprehensive energy efficiency program, which includes energy audits and the use of energy-efficient lighting, pumps, and other equipment. The port has also implemented a number of waste management initiatives, such as using efficient waste collection systems and investing in a zero-waste program. Finally, the Port of Los Angeles in the United States has implemented green port initiatives such as using clean energy sources, investing in green construction materials, and reducing air and water pollution (Mark Buzinkay, 2023). The port has also implemented a number of waste management strategies, such as using on-site composting, waste recycling, and energy recovery systems. Overall, green port initiatives offer ports worldwide the opportunity to reduce their environmental impact and achieve sustainability (Kavakeb S, Nguyen T.T., McGinley K, Yang Z,

Jenkinson I, Murray R. 2015). By investing in green technology, renewable energy sources, container terminal automation, and efficient waste management strategies, ports can make a significant contribution to the fight against climate change.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper collected data in three dimensions, literature review was primarily conducted in issues related with ports' role in maritime transport and shipping industry, how to become smart port in global changes. What is future direction of smart port development. Secondly, survey method was used to examine issues and relationships between studying variables. Finally, in-depth interview was conducted to obtain more deep information from port users, port operators and port regulators. The population consisted of 90 companies in Thailand. Deploying random stratified sampling, questionnaires were distributed to 110 companies. After a month, there were 90 questionnaires returned with 81.8 per cent response rate.

The conceptual framework was derived from theoretical studies (Theppitak, T., 2023). The study investigate relationship between variables related with issues of smart port development and dynamic changes of shipping and maritime industry, including how to develop Thai ports to become smart and green port.

3.1 Research Questions

The objective of this paper is to explores current status of Thai ports, and future direction of seaport and maritime transport in next decade. It studies role of seaports, especially Thai port to drive economic growth and to create national competitiveness. Furthermore, it also examines what factors influencing to future port development and port survival. It studies how port can adapt and survive sustainably in global changes and disruptions.

1. What is current status of Thai ports, and future direction of seaport and maritime transport in next decade?
2. What are factors influencing to future port development and port survival?
3. How port can adapt and survive sustainably in global changes and disruptions?
4. What is a conceptual model of green and smart ports?

3.2 Population & Sampling Procedure

Eisenhardt (1989) stated that selection of an appropriate population controlled extraneous variation and helped to define the limits for generalizing the findings. The paper was quantitative research by applying inferential statistics which using a small number of parts of the whole population to make inferences, judgments and conclusions about a population on the basis of a sample (Zikmund, 1997).

The study used companies as members in Bangkok Shipowners and Agents Association (BSAA), Thai Shipowner's Association (TSA), and Thai International Freight Forwarders Association (TIFFA) and Thai National Shoppers' Council (TNSC). They are a non-profit organization, which are established to work collaboratively with Thai ports. 110 questionnaires were randomly distributed to the targeted companies. After a month, there were 90 valid questionnaires returned with response rate of 81.8 per cent

3.3 Validity and Reliability

The items of questionnaires were perceptual Likert scales (Rossi et al., 1983) by targeted samples were asked to rate each item on a five-point scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. If a variable was related to a complex concept (Fowler, 1984), it was multi-item and its value

corresponded to the mean value of the scales. In determining measurement properties of the constructs used in the statistical analysis, reliability and validity were assessed (Dick and Hagerty, 1971), by using respectively Cronbach's alpha and principal component analysis. Reliability had two components stability (in time) and equivalence (in term of means and variances of different measures of the same construct). The main instruments for the reliability assessment were the "test-retest method" (for stability) and Cronbach's alpha (for equivalence).

The designed questionnaire based on literature review and interviews from a panel of experts in port and shipping industry. The reliability analysis of scale in research instrument yielded favorable results. The construct exhibited high degree of reliability in term of coefficient alpha. The alpha value of overall questionnaire was 0.82. Nunnally and Bernstein (1995); Anderson and Gerbing (1988) suggested that value of reliability at 0.70 was acceptable, however if those over 0.80 was good (Sekaran, 2000).

Validity was considered concerning with the content, criterion and construct (Zikmund, 1997). Content validity could not be determined statistically, but only by the experts and by referring to the literature. The researcher examined over 50 works published over years related to port operation and management, maritime transport, and shipping industry. Criterion validity concerned to the predictive nature of the research instrument to obtain the objective outcome. Construct validity measured whether a variable was an appropriate operational definition of the construct or not (Pearson, 1901). The construct validity was established through use of principal component analysis (PCA) to derive a small number of linear combinations (principal components) of a set of variables that retail as much of the information in the original variable as possible. These linear combinations had coefficients equal to eigenvectors of the correlation (covariance) matrix; eigenvectors were orthogonal. The principal components were sorted in descending order of eigenvalues, which were equal to the variances of the components.

3.4 Data Collection

The paper collected data in two following dimensions: first, literature review was conducted in various fields related with ports' role in maritime transport and shipping industry, how to become smart port in global changes. What is future direction of smart port development. Secondly, survey method was used to examine issues and relationships between studying variables. Finally, in-depth interview was conducted to obtain more deep information from port users, port providers and port regulators. The population consisted of 90 companies in Thailand. Deploying random stratified sampling, questionnaires were distributed to 110 companies. After a month, there were 90 questionnaires returned with 81.8 per cent response rate.

The questionnaires were randomly distributed to the sampling targets by applying a five-point Likert-type scale. The key measures based on evaluating perception both ports' role in maritime transport and shipping industry and future direction of ports. Verifying dimensionality and reliability of each construct that included factor analysis, item-to-total correlation analysis and Cronbach's alpha analysis were conducted in this study.

The questionnaires were randomly distributed by postal mail to sampling. In some circumstances, when response rate was too low and uncompleted format, another questionnaire was directly distributed to the firms by the researcher in closer area. The firms were randomly selected from the mentioned list, and ensuring that same companies (from mail questionnaires) were not surveyed repeatedly. It used same above questionnaire to ensure that response rate was sufficient and appropriate for generating, analyzing and interpreting the findings. Finally, the email questionnaires were randomly sent to web administrator of samplings.

3.5 Data Processing

After questionnaires were returned, they were classified sources of returned questionnaires, including coding and editing to make ready for data entry (Zikmund, 1997). The SPSS for Window version 14 was used for analyzing and processing the data.

4. FINDING RESULTS

Table 4: Characteristic of the respondents

Type of Business	Per Cent
1. Port Operators	32
2. Importers-Exporters	34
3. Shipping Lines	20
4. Others (e.g., Freight Forwarder, Custom Broker)	14
Total	100

Table 4 shows kind of respondents. The greatest number of respondents are importers-exporters or 34 per cent. Next, port operators (e.g., private ports and terminal leasing companies in Laem Chabang Port), and shipping lines are 32 and 20 per cent respectively.

Table 5: Duration of Business Establishment

Time Duration	Per cent
1. 1-5 Years	9
2. 5-10 Years	12
3. 10-15 Years	20
4. 15-20 Years	25
5. More than 20 Years	34
Total	100

Table 5 shows duration of business establishment. The survey reveals that time duration which respondents have established their businesses or operations in Thailand. The survey shows that greatest number of respondents or 34 per cent have established more than 20 years, and next, during 15-20 years and during 11-20 years are 25, and 20 per cent respectively. The result shows that most of respondents or 79 per cent are jointly working together in port business and shipping industry for more than 10 years.

Table 6: Proportion of Business Ownership

Description	Percent
1. Thai 100%	38
2. Thai 51% and Foreigner 49%	32
3. Foreigner 51% and Thai 49%	17
4. Foreigner 100%	13
Total	100

Table 6 reveals proportion of business ownership. The greatest number of the respondents or 38 per cent is owned 100 percent by Thais. Next, business ownerships for Thai 51% and Foreigner 49%, and Foreigner 51% and Thai 49% are equally 32 and 17 per cent respectively. While 100 per cent of business ownership is foreigner.

Table 7: Objectives and purposes of port operation and management

Main objectives and purposes	Percent
1. Providing full range of port services	28
2. Supporting for cost reduction	22
3. Responding to customer needs	19
4. Solving the customer problems	16
5. Reducing environmental footprint & emission	12
6. Others (e.g., facilitation, and keep-well inform)	3
Total	100

Table 7 represents objectives and purposes of port operation and management. The result shows that most of respondents or 28 per cent identify those ports would provide a full range of port services. Some of them point out that ports would support users or customers for cost reduction, including responding to customer needs and solving the customer problems at 22, 19 and 16 percent respectively.

Table 8: Factors influencing to adapt and transform to Thai port operation and management

Factors	Mean	S.D.
1. Intense competition	4.84	0.565
2. Reducing total logistics costs	4.63	0.764
3. Pressures from global and national economic situations	4.33	0.624
4. Technological changes and disruption	4.35	0.753
5. Pressures from government and related associations	4.28	0.653

Table 8 shows factors influencing to adapt and transform to Thai port operation and management. The study asked the respondents to rate what factors influencing to adapt and transform to Thai port operation and management. The result reveals that most of respondents points out that ports are facing intense competition (4.84). While port users require port operators to facilitate and support for their cost reduction (4.63). They are also concerning with technological changes and disruption (4.35) and Pressures from global and national economic situations (4.33). Finally, pressures from government and related associations are forces to port operations and management (4.28).

Table 9: Impacts of Technology and Innovation influencing to port operation and management

Factors	Percent
1. Artificial Intelligence (AI)	18
2. The Internet of Things (IoT)	14
3. Digitalization	19
4. Robots	12
5. Smart Machines	11
6. Cloud/Client Computing	12
7. Software-Defined Applications and Infrastructure	14
Total	100.0

Table 9 shows Impacts of Technology and Innovation influencing to port operation and management. The study asked the respondents what kind of technology and Innovation influencing to port operation and management in next decade. The result reveals that most of them identifies that development of digitalization (19 per cent) rapidly disrupts port operations in near future. Next, complex and sophisticated Artificial Intelligence (AI) would transform patterns of future work and services in ports (18 per cent). The Internet of Things (14 per cent) and Software-Defined Applications and Infrastructure (14 per cent) are adopted in various port activities, including planning and

management. While Cloud/Client Computing (12 per cent) and Robotic Machines and Equipment (12 per cent) are being widely adopted in port operations.

Fig 1: Theoretical framework of smart port development

Fig. 1 shows theoretical framework of smart port development. From the figure, developing port operations and management would be considered as series of chains. Ports are attempting to adapt and respond to shipping lines and ship agents' requirement, e.g., frequencies, port calls, ship schedules, and cargo operations. While importers-exporters are significant role to adaptation and survival of shipping line and ship agents. Finally, world market and customer behaviors would be original point, in which importers and exporters would produce their products to respond global market.

Figure 2: Hypothesis and relationship between variables

Figure 2 shows hypothesis and relationship between variables. According to review the literature, the studies reveal that developing port to be green and smart port is major driven to survive in intense competition in global dynamic changes. While modern technologies provide the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics processes. The efficiency and safety of the cargo flows highly depend on the related information flows.

The shipping industry is a major contributor to global emissions. Therefore, it would develop measures and strategies to reduce its environmental footprint. The key to improving the sustainability of the shipping industry lies in green port initiatives. In this research is to explore a relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and port effectiveness and efficiency, and sustainable growth (Y).

The hypothesis is based on the more developing port to be green and smart port, it facilitates more on port effectiveness and efficiency, and increasing sustainable growth. Furthermore, it examines a relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and technological changes and disruptions (Z). It is based on hypothesis that green and smart port strategy and adaptability would be adapted, according to technological changes and disruptions.

5. RESEARCH DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

When considering the kind of respondents covers in port business and shipping industry, by companies have been operating their businesses more than 20 years. It means that doing the businesses, companies need to jointly work together as global supply chain. While most of companies is joint venture with proportion of business ownership at Thai 51% and Foreigner 49%.

The study shows that stakeholders expect port operation by firstly providing a full range of port services, including supporting users or customers for cost reduction, and solving the customer problems. Considering factors influencing to adapt and transform to Thai port operation and management, the research reveals that ports are facing intense competition nationally and globally. Countries attempt to encourage and boost port efficiency and productivity. Port users expect that port operators would facilitate and support for their cost reduction.

Even though, Ports face competition between ports and also competition between port terminals. Technological changes and disruption are another factor which influencing to adapt and transform to Thai port operation and management. Globalization and technological developments have not only affected the design and operations of port facilities, but also the organizational and institutional relationship between members of the port community.

Modern technologies provide the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics processes; hence they create an effective advance which strengthens the port's position among the maritime communities. Further, disruptions for example, COVID-19 pandemic, can extremely affect to port survival. While ports face from pressures by global and national economic situations, geopolitics, Russia-Ukraine Crisis, and world trade wars. Other factor is government, International Maritime Organization, and related associations have also role to enforce ports to provide measure for port safety, security and environment.

There are some international regulations related to the prevention of marine pollution e.g., MARPOL73/78 and greenhouse gas emissions, including the increase in social and economic demands is causing that port around the world to incorporate initiatives to reduce environmental impact and improve port operations.

Developing a smart port, it needs to provide modernized port technology and innovation for port operation and management. The study reveals that development of digitalization and complex and sophisticated Artificial Intelligence (AI) are firstly considering to increase port competitiveness. The Internet of Things and Software-Defined Applications and Infrastructure would transform patterns of future works and services in ports and hinterland, including adopted in various port activities, and port planning and management. Finally, Cloud/Client Computing and Robotic Machines and Equipment are a newcomer and being widely adopted in port operations.

Fig 3: Theoretical framework of smart and green port development

Fig. 3 shows theoretical framework of smart and green port development. To discuss the framework, considering port development, operations and management would be considered as series of chains. Ports are attempting to adapt and respond to shipping lines and ship agents’ requirement. While shipping lines and ship agents would monitor their customer demands, e.g., volumes of cargo, frequencies of port calls. However, for importers-exporters perspective, they would focus on changes of world market and customer behaviors so that they can adapt and respond to sell their products internationally. When considering the figure, world market and customer behaviors would be original point, in which importers and exporters would produce their products to respond global market. Generally, ports adapt and respond to shipping line and importers-exporters. However, world market and customer behaviors are complex and sophisticated, including rapidly changing. The question is that how can port analytically understand about future demands of world market and customer behavior?

The study reveals that the smart and green port concept is based on the ability of new technologies to transform port service into interactive and dynamic businesses, more efficient and transparent. Its objective is to satisfy the needs of customers and users without forgetting its responsibility to the city and the citizens. The digitization combined with careful planning and management of port operations allows us to find smart solution to optimized logistics and environmental impacts to promote efficiency and to enhance the safety of both seaports and coastal regions involved.

Table 10: Summary of hypothesis testing and relationship between variables

Variable		Correlation	p-value
Independent	Dependent		
X	Y	0.812	0.000*
X	Z	0.624	0.000*

Table 10 presents summary of hypothesis testing and measuring a relationship between variables. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and port effectiveness and efficiency, and sustainable growth (Y). Developing port to be green and smart port, it increasingly provides port effectiveness and efficiency, and increasing sustainable growth. It also reveals that there is a relationship between green and smart port strategy and management (X) and technological changes and disruptions (Z). It is based on hypothesis that green and smart port strategy and management would be adapted consistent with technological changes and disruptions.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Global ports and maritime shipping industry are important carriers for global supply chain networks. While modern seaports have a significant role in supply chain for the competitiveness of each country in terms of globalization and connectivity. The study shows that green and smart port is major driven to survive in intense competition in global dynamic changes. Modern technologies provide the optimization, the management, and the automation of the port operation and the logistics activities; hence they create an effective advance which strengthens the port's position among the maritime communities.

Furthermore, the shipping industry is a major contributor to global emissions, but it is also one of the most promising sectors to reduce its environmental footprint. The key to improving the sustainability of the shipping industry lies in green port initiatives. Ports worldwide are feeling the need to become environmentally friendly, whether by transitioning to Net Zero Carbon, reducing emissions, or operating more sustainably. Future direction to enhance development of green and smart port strategies: Energy efficiency and alternative energy; Green ports certification; Emergency environment protection/Diester preparedness; Compliance with international/national legislation; Marine water quality management; Light and noise pollution management; and Port operational efficiency. The strategies would include port technology and innovation investment, smart manpower and cultural development.

7. FUTURE RESEARCH

This paper explores current status of Thai ports, and future direction of port to enhance port performance and competitiveness. The main purpose of this paper is to enhance port competitiveness and developing to be a smart and green port. But there are totally 138 ports covering 109 cargo ports and fishery ports in Thailand. Therefore, in future research, it would specifically focus on potential ports in Thailand.

In this research, data collection is collected through questionnaire and in-depth interview. The samplings cover importers-exporters, port operators, and shipping lines a ship agent to examine and analyze their expectation and perception. In future, it would include port regulator and government agencies e.g., Marine Department, and Customs Department.

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